

MOTOR NEURON DISEASES

May 2019

MOTOR NEURON DISEASES

MND involves all diseases that involve selective loss of function of the upper and / or lower motor neurons innervating the voluntary musculature of the limbs and bulbar regions.

CLASSIFICATION

AMYOTROPHIC LATERAL SCLEROSIS

AMYOTROPHIC LATERAL SCLEROSIS (ALS)

- First described in 1897.
- Referred as “Lou Gehrig” disease.
- A progressive neuromuscular condition characterized by combined upper and lower motor neuron signs.

CLINICAL TYPES AND PATTERNS

- Sporadic
- Genetically determined
- ALS plus syndromes
- ALS with laboratory abnormalities of uncertain significance
- ALS- Mimic syndromes

ALS WITH LABORATORY ABNORMALITIES OF UNCERTAIN SIGNIFICANCE (ALS-LAUS) SYNDROMES

(1) Monoclonal gammopathy

Monoclonal gammopathy of unknown significance, Waldenstrom's macroglobulinemia, osteosclerotic myeloma, etc.

(2) Autoantibodies

High-titer GMI ganglioside antibody; etc.

(3) Nonmalignant endocrine abnormalities

Hyperthyroidism, hyperparathyroidism, hypogonadism, etc.

(4) Lymphoma

(Hodgkin's and non-Hodgkin's lymphoma). Cases of sporadic ALS associated with cancer of the lung, colon or thyroid and insulinoma, is currently thought not to be causally related to the neoplasm.

(5) Infection

HIV-1, HTLV-1, varicella-zoster, brucellosis, borreliosis, cat-scratch disease, syphilis

(6) Exogenous toxins

Lead, mercury, aluminum

ALS-PLUS AND ALS-MIMIC SYNDROMES

(1) Geographic clustering

Western Pacific, Guam, Kii Peninsula, North Africa, Madras, etc.

(2) Extrapyrarnidal signs

Bradykinesia; cogwheel rigidity; tremor; familial or sporadic

(3) Cerebellar degeneration

Spinocerebellar abnormalities; familial or sporadic

(4) Dementia

Familial or sporadic; frontal lobe type; Creutzfeldt-Jacob amyotrophic form

(5) Autonomic nervous system involvement

Clinically significant abnormal cardiovascular reflexes; sphincteric problems

(6) Objective sensory abnormalities

Decreased vibration; sharp/dull discrimination; blunting of cold sensation

(7) Ocular movement abnormalities

Supranuclear; nuclear; familial or sporadic

(8) ALS mimics

Delayed post-poliomyelitis; multifocal motor neuropathy with or without conduction block; endocrinopathies; lead intoxication; infections

EPIDEMIOLOGY

- 1-2/ 100,000
- Males > females 2:1
- 90-95% sporadic
- 5-10% inherited AD, AR
- Onset >40 years
- Increase with age

AETIOLOGY

Unknown

Multifactorial Genetic
 Viral
 Autoimmune
 Neurotoxicity hypothesis

RISK FACTORS

Trauma

Long bone fracture

Manual work

Occupational exposure to toxins; lead;
 Solvents

Foods

PATHOLOGY

- Loss of large motor neurons in spinal cord & brainstem
- Gliosis
- Spheroids (interwoven disorganized neurofilaments in proximal axons)
- Bunina bodies (intracytoplasmic inclusion bodies)
- Loss of giant Betz cells
- Other neuronal loss in DRG & Clarkes' nucleus
- 1/3 of motoneurons destroyed before muscle atrophy becomes apparent
- PN shows secondary degeneration of axons & myelin
- Surviving motoneurons developed collaterals branches
- Atrophy of the degenerated muscles

PROGNOSIS

- Average survival is 3-5 years after the onset
- Death occur from respiratory failure ,insufficiency
- Bulbar onset worst prognosis
 - 20 months is the median survival*
 - 5% survive 5 years after the onset*
- Spinal onset
 - 29 months is the median survival*
 - 15% survive 5 years after the onset*
- Short survival associated with
 - Greater age*
 - Lower percent-predicted vital capacity (FVC%)*
 - Lower serum chloride*
 - Short interval from symptom onset to diagnosis*
 - Greater weight loss*
- Subacute & reversible type was recorded

POORER PROGNOSIS FOR SURVIVAL

- Clinical

- Increasing age
- Prominent recent weight loss
- Short time from onset to diagnosis
- Rapid rate of strength & respiratory loss during 6 months after diagnosis
- Respiratory failure
- No gastrostomy

- Laboratory

- Poor pulmonary function < 60% of predicted
- Serum chloride: Falling; relation to poor nutrition
- EMG

Low CMAPs

Decrement on RNS

EMG: Marked jitter; Low fiber density

- Homozygous deletion of [SMN2 gene5](#)

More common in sporadic ALS

Survival time: 2 years short

CLINICAL PRESENTATIONS

- UMN signs (weakness, spasticity, hyperreflexia, extensor planter)
- LMN signs (weakness, wasting, fasciculations)
- Cachexia
- No sphincteric or sexual disturbances
- cerebellar signs
- sensory changes
- cognitive changes
- oculomotor dysfunction
- autonomic nervous system dysfunction

LOWER MOTOR NEURON AND UPPER MOTOR NEURON SIGNS IN FOUR CNS REGIONS

	Brainstem	Cervical	Thoracic	Lumbosacral
Lower motor neuron signs weakness, atrophy, fasciculations	jaw, face, palate, tongue, larynx	neck, arm, hand, diaphragm	back, abdomen	back, abdomen, leg, foot
Upper motor neuron signs pathologic spread of reflexes, clonus, etc.	clonic jaw gag reflex exaggerated snout reflex pseudobulbar features forced yawning pathologic DTR's spastic tone	clonic DTR's Hoffman reflex pathologic DTR's spastic tone preserved reflex in weak wasted limb	loss of superficial abdominal reflexes pathologic DTR's spastic tone	clonic DTR's - extensor plantar response pathologic DTR's spastic tone preserved reflex in weak wasted limb

POSITIVE FEATURES

- **Definite ALS**
 - LMN and UMN signs in three to four regions
 - Evidence of progression
- **Probable ALS**
 - LMN and UMN signs in at least two regions with UMN above LMN signs and evidence of progression
- **Possible ALS**
 - LMN and UMN in one region
 - UMN in two regions
 - LMN above UMN signs
 - LMN and UMN signs but no evidence of progression
- **Suspected ALS**
 - LMN signs in two to three regions

NEGATIVE FEATURES

- Findings inconsistent with diagnosis of ALS
- Neuroimaging, EMG, clinical or other evidence of an alternative disease explaining signs or symptoms
- Lack of progression to other body regions
- Cognitive decline
- Sphincter abnormalities
- Sensory dysfunction
- Visual decline

DIFFERENTIAL DIAGNOSIS

- Multifocal motor neuropathy with conduction block (MMNCB)
- Myasthenia gravis
- Multiple sclerosis
- Pseudobulbar palsy
- Myopathy
- Postpolio syndrome
- Monomelic muscular atrophy
- Reversible MND
- Denny Brown, Foley syndrome

DIAGNOSIS

Electrophysiological studies:

Active denervation
Fibrillation potentials
Positive sharp waves

Chronic denervation
Large MUAP increase duration
increase amplitude
polyphasicity
Decrease interference pattern
Unstable MUAP

The combination of active and chronic denervations is required but the relative proportion may vary from muscles to others.

DIAGNOSIS

Lamberts' EMG criteria for ALS:

- Fibrillation & fasciculation potentials in the upper & lower limbs or hands plus upper or lower limb.
- Increase amplitude & duration of MUAP with decrease recruitment & normal NCS allowing reduced CMAP & related slowing of MCV.

DIAGNOSIS

LABOTATERY STUDIES:

- Magnetic stimulation

Absent or prolonged cortical motor evoked potential

- MRI

BRAIN focal atrophy of precentral gyrus

SPINE normal

- PET scan

Reduced glucose consumption in pericentral area

- Central motor conduction times

Prolonged

- Others

Normal CSF; serum CK; MS panel

TREATMENT

DISEASE MODIFYING DRUGS

- Riluzole** - *decrease glutamate release*
- *100 mg / day*
 - *decrease need for tracheostomy 56.8%*
 - *after 18 months vs 50.4% for placebo*
 - *adverse effects; asthma, nausea,*
 - *dizziness, granulocytopenia, increase*
 - *transaminase level*

Mecaserin

TREATMENT

SYMPTOMATIC TREATMENT

1. SIALOORRHEA

Amitriptyline

Benzotropine

Trihexaphenidyl HCL

Transdermal hyoscine (scopalamine)

Propranolol decrease thick mucus production

Physical measures:

Suction machine

Manual assisted coughing techniques

In-Exsufflator cough machine

External beam irradiation to a single parotid gland

TREATMENT

SYMPTOMATIC TREATEMENT

2. NUTRITION & DYSPHAGIA

Modification of the food & fluid consistency

Coaching by speech pathologist

PEG

TREATMENT

SYMPTOMATIC TREATEMENT

3. RESPIRATORY INSUFFICIENCY

Non invasive ventilatory support

Respiratory therapist consultation

Ventilatory assisted respiration

TREATMENT

SYMPTOMATIC TREATEMENT

4. DEPRESSION & ANXIETY

Tricyclic antidepressant

SSRIs

Supportive & family therapy

TREATMENT

SYMPTOMATIC TREATEMENT

5. ANTI- SPASTISITY

Baclofen

Tizanidine

Diazepam

Dantrolene

Streching-exercise

TREATMENT

SYMPTOMATIC TREATEMENT

6. FASCICULATION

Lorazepam

Decrease caffeine & nicotine intake

TREATMENT

SYMPTOMATIC TREATEMENT

7. PAIN

NSAIDs

Anticonvulsant Tegretol, Phenytoin

Tricyclic antidepressant

TREATMENT

INEFFECTIVE TREATMENT

- Branched chain amino acids
- Immunosuppressive therapy

IVIG

Cyclophosphamide

fludarabine

- Total lymphoid irradiation
- Free radicle scavenger
- Dextromethorphan

ALS-like disorders with Fronto-Temporal Dementia

Onset age: 4th to 8th decade

Clinical:

Fronto-Temporal Dementia (FTD)

Dementia

Language disorders

Personality changes

Behavioral disorders

Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis syndrome (ALS)

Bulbar dysfunction: Dysphagia

Limb denervation

Upper motor neuron signs in limbs

Hyperreflexia

Spasticity less prominent in some patients

Fasciculations: May occur without signs of ALS

Course & associations:

ALS or FTD may present first

Time between onset of syndromes may be years

Most commonly dementia presents first

Association

14% of FTD patients meet criteria for definite ALS

36% of FTD patients meet criteria for possible ALS

Laboratory

EMG: Denervation; Fasciculations

CNS Pathology

Neuronal loss in frontotemporal lobes

Intraneuronal ubiquitin-immunoreactive inclusions

Frequency

ALS-Dementia: 100%

Non-demented ALS patients: 20% to 50%

Frontotemporal dementia lacking motor symptoms: Some patients

Locations

Hippocampal dentate granular cells

Neurons in layer II of frontotemporal (extra-motor) cortex

Dystrophic cortical neurites

Motor neurons

Histochemistry

Ubiquitin: Staining

Tau & α -Synuclein: No staining

Cortex: Astrocytosis (Layer V); Loss of Betz cells

Loss of pyramidal tract axons: More distally

No pathological evidence of other dementing conditions

HEREDITARY SPASTIC PARAPARESIS

HEREDITARY SPASTIC PARAPARESIS (HSP)

HSP is a genetically and clinically heterogeneous syndromes.

It is divided into

Pure HSP

Complex HSP with additional neurological features .

- *Mental retardation*
- *Ataxia (specially in UL)*
- *Muscle wasting*
- *Skin changes*
- *Optic atrophy*
- *Extrapyramidal feature*
- *Sensory polyneuropathy*

HEREDITARY SPASTIC PARAPARESIS (HSP)

Pure

Complex

PURE HSP (STRUMPELL – LORRAIN DISEASE)

Pure HSP is inherited as AD, AR, and X – Linked types

Autosomal dominant HSP

Linkage to loci on either chromosome 2, 8, 10, 12, 14, 15.

Mutation of spastin or paraplegin gene on chromosome 2.

High penetrance with variable expression in families.

Insidious onset.

Variable onset either before or after 35y.

PURE HSP (STRUMPELL – LORRAIN DISEASE)

Pathology

Degeneration of the corticospinal with loss prominent involvement of dorsal column & spinocerebellar tracts, motor, and anterior horn cells.

PURE HSP (STRUMPELL – LORRAIN DISEASE)

Clinical presentation

- Lower limbs spasticity, extensor plantar .
- Spasticity out of proportion of weakness.
- Upper limbs may be involved.
- Impairment of vibration sense, ankle areflexia.
- Distal muscle wasting & bladder dysfunction
- +ve family history
- Progression in late onset is very rapid.

PURE HSP (STRUMPELL – LORRAIN DISEASE)

Diagnosis

Exclude treatable

Focal spinal cord disease.

Vitamine B12 deficiency.

Multiple sclerosis (progressive spinal type)

Dopa- responsive dystonia.

Somatosensory evoked potential may be abnormal.

Central motor conduction is minimally affected.

PURE HSP (STRUMPELL – LORRAIN DISEASE)

Autosomal recessive

Very rare.

Loci on chromosome 8, 15, 16.

X- Linked pure HSP

Genetically heterogeneous

Female carrier are normal

Genetic linkage to proteolipid protein (PLP) ; xq22

Mutation of the same gene produce
complex HSP

Pelizaeus Merzbacher disease

Clinically similar to early onset AD type,

COMPLEX HSP

Sjogren Larsson syndrome

AR, present at birth

HSP, ichthyosis, mental retardation, retinopathy.

Behr syndrome *AR, HSP, optic atrophy*

Kjellin syndrome *HSP, mental retardation, retinal degeneration*

Complex HSP *with severe sensory neuropathy & mutilating LL acropathy*

Complex HSP *with distal muscle wasting*

Complex HSP *with cerebellar ataxia*

Allan Herndon *MR, hypotonia, motor delay, ataxia*

MASA syndrome *MR, aphasia, shuffling gait, adducted thumb*

PRIMARY LATERAL SCLEROSIS

PRIMARY LATERAL SCLEROSIS (PLS)

Progressive degenerative disease of the upper motor neurons .

Affect lower extremities, trunk, upper extremities, bulbar muscles (in that order)

PRIMARY LATERAL SCLEROSIS (PLS)

Epidemiology

0.01 /100,000

Male > female

30 – 66 yrs median age 50 yrs (< 20 yrs is recorded)

Etiology unknown

Pathology loss of Betz cells in precentral gyrus

PRIMARY LATERAL SCLEROSIS (PLS)

Clinical picture

UMN in LL, trunk, arm, bulbar muscles.
Signs of other system affection not present

Pringles' diagnostic criteria

Insidious onset

Spastic paraparesis in adult

No family history of similar condition

Symmetrical spastic paraparesis

Slow progression of 3 years duration

PRIMARY LATERAL SCLEROSIS (PLS)

Investigations

Laboratory

Routine lab

VDRL

Lyme

HTLV-1

CSF glucose, protein, IgG, MS panel

PRIMARY LATERAL SCLEROSIS (PLS)

Investigations

Radiological

MRI BRAIN ⇨ *Atrophy of frontoparietal region*

MRI SPINE ⇨ *Normal*

MRS ⇨ *Abnormal NAA / Creatine ratio*

SPECT ⇨ *Decrease uptake of motor cortex*

PET ⇨ *Decrease glucose consumption*

PRIMARY LATERAL SCLEROSIS (PLS)

Investigations

Electrophysiological

Motor evoked potential absent or delayed

Peripheral conduction is normal

Minimal denervation activity

PRIMARY LATERAL SCLEROSIS (PLS)

DD:

→ Spinal cord lesions

Tumors, lymphoma, syringomyelia, vascular malformations

→ Spinal bone lesions

spondylosis, cervical rib, metastatic tumors

→ Infections

HIV, syphilis, myelitis, poliomyelitis, Lyme disease

→ Endocrine disorders

Hyperthyroidism, hyperparathyroidism, diabetic radiculopathy

→ Toxins

Lead, mercury

→ Other

Postpolio syndrome, Huntington's disease, Friedreich's ataxia, sarcoidosis, multiple sclerosis, polymyositis, myasthenia gravis, muscular dystrophies

PRIMARY LATERAL SCLEROSIS (PLS) *RECESSIVE, JUVENILE ONSET*

Chromosome 2q33

- **Gene mutations**

- **PLS:** Deletion in exon 9
- **ALS2:** Mutation in another region of alsin gene
- **Familial spastic paraparesis, infantile onset**

- **Clinical**

- **Onset:** Childhood **Spasticity:** Bulbar; Extremities
- **Gaze paresis** **Normal:** Cognition; Sensation

- **Laboratory**

- **Central motor conduction times:** Delayed or Unrecordable
- **EMG:** No denervation

KONZO

Tropical myelopathy

Dietary cyanide exposure

Abrupt onset

Symmetric spastic paraparesis

Non-progressive

Permanent

NEUROLATHYRISM

- Oral daily consumption of the chickling pea vetch (lathyrus sativus)
- Excitotoxic B-N oxaylamino-l-alanine (BOAA)
- Spastic paraparesis

MONOMELIC AMYOTROPHY

Eponyms

Hirayama's disease: Progressive weakness over 1 to 3 years, then plateau

O'Sullivan-McLeod syndrome: Slow progression

Onset: Young adult; 15 to 25 years; Up to 40 years in India

Epidemiology

Male > Female

Occasional familial occurrence

Common in Eastern India

MONOMELIC AMYOTROPHY

Clinical:

Weakness Often confined to a single arm

Distal: C7, C8 & T1 innervated muscles

Atrophy: "Oblique amyotrophy"; Sparing brachioradialis

Occasional other features

Weakness *Ipsilateral shoulder*

Progression to opposite limb

Worsening on exposure to cold

Fasciculations: *On affected side (66%); May not be symptomatic*

Sensory loss: *Mild*

Tremor: *On finger extension*

MONOMELIC AMYOTROPHY

Disease course

Hirayama syndrome: Progression over 1 to 3 yrs; Then static

O'Sullivan-McLeod syndrome: Progression over decades

Laboratory

EMG: *Chronic denervation, in affected limb(s), lower extremities in some*

NCV: *Small CMAPs in affected limbs*

MRI: *inelastic dura: Spinal cord compression with neck flexion*

Other studies

No major spinal anomalies

Spinal cord atrophy: C6 & C7

T2 signal in anterior horns of gray matter

Mild flexion-induced cord displacement

MONOMELIC AMYOTROPHY

Differential diagnosis

- Proximal lower motor neuron syndrome
- ALS
 - Sporadic
 - Hereditary
 - SOD mutations: A4V, Leu84Val, D101N

Pathology

- Loss of motor neurons in anterior horn of spinal cord
- Shrinkage of remaining motor neurons
- Inclusion bodies: Intracytoplasmic, Hyaline

PRIMARY MUSCULAR ATROPHY (PMA)

Widespread Lower Motor Neuron Syndrome

Clinical:

Weakness: *Distribution*

Distal & Proximal: Either may be more prominent

Asymmetric

Often involves paraspinous & respiratory muscles

Often spares bulbar musculature

Spontaneous motor activity

Cramps: Common in legs, at night

Fasciculations

No *upper motor neuron signs*

Pain: *Related to immobility*

PRIMARY MUSCULAR ATROPHY (PMA)

Time course

Progressive

Similar to, more rapid, or slower than, typical ALS

Laboratory

Muscle pathology: *Grouped atrophy > Fiber type grouping*

No *serum antibodies*

No *conduction block*

No evidence for response to treatment

INHERITED SPINAL MUSCULAR ATROPHY (SMA)

HEREDITARY MOTOR NEURONOPATHIES

A) Werdnig Hoffman ; type 1 SMA

- AR, 5q11.2, SMN mutation in 98%
- NAIP gene mutation in 20-50%
- Fatal by age 3 years
- Absent or weak fetal movement
- Normal at birth
- Deformity, contracture, and dislocation affect the limbs at birth
- Severe form hypotonia, weak sucking, die within a year

INHERITED SPINAL MUSCULAR ATROPHY (SMA)

A) Werdnig Hoffman ; type 1 SMA

- Delayed motor milestone, weak cry and feeding
- Characteristic frog like position
- Areflexia, wasting, face spared, tongue is involved
- Normal eye movement, sensory and social responses
- Prognosis

Respiratory failure

Death: 50% by 7 months; 95% by 17 months

Chronic course in 5%

INHERITED SPINAL MUSCULAR ATROPHY (SMA)

B) SMA 2 intermediate form

SMN mutation in 90%

NAIP uncommon

Later onset > 6 months, less severe

Scoliosis developed, tendon reflexes is preserved

Spontaneous arrest of the disease may occur

INHERITED SPINAL MUSCULAR ATROPHY (SMA)

C) SMA 3 (KUGELBERG-WELANDER) disease

Chronic progressive proximal muscle weakness

25% associated calf hypertrophy

Facial weakness, kyphoscoliosis,,

Respiratory and bulbar involvement is unusual

Normal life expectancy

INHERITED SPINAL MUSCULAR ATROPHY (SMA)

D) SMA 4, adult-onset proximal form

AR or AD inheritance

Age 15 - 60 years

Progressive proximal muscle weakness

Bulbar involvement is unusual

INHERITED SPINAL MUSCULAR ATROPHY (SMA)

E) Distal SMA

AD or AR inheritance

Variable ages, AD common < 20 years

Normal sensory response, retained reflexes even ankle reflex

Legs > arms

AR form at 15 - 25 years

Gastrocnemius > peroneal and tibialis anterior

CK is tenfolds increase

INHERITED SPINAL MUSCULAR ATROPHY (SMA)

f) Scapuloperoneal muscular atrophy

Age 15-25years

Distal leg weakness followed by shoulder girdle few years later

Sparing intrinsic muscle of the foot

Sensory abnormalities may developed

AD neurogenic scapuloperoneal amyotrophy

Congenital absence of some muscles

Laryngeal palsy

Males > females

INHERITED SPINAL MUSCULAR ATROPHY (SMA)

G) Hexoseaminidase deficiency

AR GM1 gangliosidosis

Pure motor neuron either LMN or UMN

Other abnormalities; cerebellar ataxia, dementia

Common in Ashkenazi jews

Decrease hexoseaminidase level

HEREDITARY BULBAR PALSY

A) x-linked bulbospinal neuronopathy (kennedy syndrome)

- ☆ Only in men, in 20-40years
- ☆ Limb cramps, weakness predominate in legs
- ☆ Mild severe bulbar , wasted tongue
- ☆ Dysphagia and dytharthria 20 years later
- ☆ Marked fasciculations in face and tongue
- ☆ Grimace evoked contractions of lower facial muscles

HEREDITARY BULBAR PALSY

A) x-linked bulbospinal neuronopathy (kennedy syndrome)

- ★ Slow progression, life expectancy not seriously affected
- ★ No signs of UMN
- ★ SNAP absent or diminished despite normal sensory examination
- ★ 25% associated DM
- ★ Androgene gene defect
- ★ Impotence and gynaecomastia

HEREDITARY BULBAR PALSY

B) Brown- violetto- van laere syndrome

- ☆ Progressive bulbar palsy
- ☆ Sensorineural deafness
- ☆ Progressive palsy of lower six cranial nerves
- ☆ 10-20 years
- ☆ Respiratory failure and death by thirties
- ☆ Clinical heterogeneity
 - *Ataxia*
 - *Optic atrophy*
 - *Muscle denervation*
 - *UMN features*

HEREDITARY BULBAR PALSY

C) fazio-londe disease

- ☆ First 5 years
- ☆ Severe bulbar symptoms
- ☆ Stridor, dysphagia, dysarthria
- ☆ Limb weakness 2 years later

PARANEOPLASTIC MOTOR NEUROPATHY

Onset: After diagnosis of tumor

Epidemiology: Majority male & > 50 years

Clinical:

Weakness

Asymmetric; Arms > Legs

Mild

Lower motor neuron only

Bulbar Normal

Cramps: Painful, Painless in some patients

PARANEOPLASTIC MOTOR NEUROPATHY

Course: Progressive then stabilizes or improves
Associated with Non-Hodgkin Lymphoma, other lymphomas & myeloproliferative disorders

Laboratory

CSF: No cells; Mildly increased protein

MRI: Spinal cord normal

Neuronopathy

PARANEOPLASTIC Lower Motor Neuron Syndrome

Epidemiology: Single patient, 72 year old female
Onset: 4 months before diagnosis of tumor

Clinical : **Weakness** *Asymmetric at on*

Arms & Legs

Severe

Lower motor neuron only

Bulbar: *Hypophonia; Dysphagia; Unilateral facial paresis*

Painless Course

Progressive over months

Improvement after tumor removal

Long-term residual disability

Sensation: *Normal*

Tendon reflexes: *Absent*

CNS *transient dizziness & Nystagmus*

PARANEOPLASTIC Lower Motor Neuron Syndrome

Associated with Ductal adenocarcinoma of breast

Laboratory Antibodies

Serum binding to bIV spectrin, isoform I (Bands at MW 250kD & 140kD)

Serum binding to axon initial segments & nodes of Ranvier in rat brain

Electrophysiology EMG: Denervation

NCV: Small CMAPs; No conduction block

MRI: Spinal cord with high signal spots on T2

Immunosuppressive treatment: No response

MULTIFOCAL MOTOR NEUROPATHY(MMN)

Epidemiology

- Male > Female: 2 to 1
- Prevalence: 1 per 100,000

Genetics: Higher frequency of homozygous SMN2 deletion (40%) than controls (10%)

Onset

- **Age**
 - *Mean 40 years*
 - *Range 25 to 70 years*
 - *Most between 30 and 50 years*
- **Weakness**
 - *Arm: Distal*
 - *Often in distribution of individual nerve: Wrist or finger extension*

MULTIFOCAL MOTOR NEUROPATHY(MMN)

Clinical Features

Weakness: 100%

Distal > Proximal (87%)

Asymmetric (94%)

Upper > Lower extremity (80%)

Fatigue: Occasional

Rare involvement: Cranial nerves 2%; Respiratory 1%

Muscle atrophy (80%)

Common in some muscles: > 90%

Bulk may be relatively preserved in weak muscles

Especially when conduction block in nerve

More common early in disease course

Fasciculations: 25% to 50%

Cramps: 50%

No UMN signs

Sensory: Normal or minimal subjective symptoms

Tendon reflexes

Preserved in proportion to strength

Normal in 40%

MULTIFOCAL MOTOR NEUROPATHY(MMN)

Time course

Weakness

Slowly progressive over 1 to 30 years (90%)

Occasionally stepwise (10%)

Transient exacerbations: Weeks to months

Pregnancy

Corticosteroid treatment

Focal conduction block: Often persists over time

Axonal loss: Often progresses over years

Death due to disease: Rare

Spontaneous remission: Rare; Not when anti-GM1 antibodies present

MULTIFOCAL MOTOR NEUROPATHY(MMN)

Electrophysiology

- Motor Conduction Block: Especially

50% Reduction of proximal vs distal CMAP amplitude

Focal

Location: Distal nerve segment in arm; Ulnar or Median nerves

May increase with activity or repeated action potentials

More regions with block in patients with long disease course (> 10 years)

- Other signs of demyelination (Mild)

Conduction velocities: Often normal between regions of block

Temporal dispersion: Mild

Distal latencies: Occasionally prolonged

- Axonal Loss

Motor, Later in disease course, Progressive reduction over time

- Sensory nerve conductions: Normal

MULTIFOCAL MOTOR NEUROPATHY(MMN)

Laboratory

- Serum M-Protein: Occasional
- CSF protein: Mildly elevated in 33%
- MRI: T2 signal intensity in region of conduction block
- Serum Autoantibodies
- Antigens: GM1 ganglioside
- Antibody type: IgM
- Optimal anti-GM1 antibody testing: Covalent ELISA

MULTIFOCAL MOTOR NEUROPATHY(MMN)

Pathology: Multifocal demyelination

- Segmental demyelination
- Onion bulbs in regions of conduction block
- Motor axon loss

Treatment

- **General**
 - Improvement with IVIg
 - *More likely*
 - *When conduction block detected*
 - *More nerves involved*
 - *May occur in mildly or severely weak patients*
 - Improvement rare or less prominent in patients with uncertain diagnosis of MMN
 - *Paraspinous denervation*
 - *Prominent muscle atrophy*

MULTIFOCAL MOTOR NEUROPATHY(MMN)

Cyclophosphamide

1 gm/M2 per month x 6 ± Preceding Plasma Exchange x2

Outcome

Improvement in 80%

Especially when titers of anti-GM1 antibodies reduced

Onset of improvement after 3 to 6 months

Duration of improvement: 1 to 5 years

Rituxan: *May be useful; Few side effects*

Interferon-b1a: *Minor improvement*

Other: Fludarabine

**NOT PREDNISONE: PREDNISONE MAY CAUSE
INCREASED WEAKNESS**

HOPKINS' SYNDROME

ACUTE POST-ASTHMATIC AMYOTROPHY

Age: 1 to 13 years

Onset: After acute asthmatic attack:

Clinical:

Latency 1 to 18 days

Mild pain: Limb, neck or meningismus Rapid onset weakness

Weakness Single limb; Asymmetric; May be Proximal > Distal

Severity: Mild to severe, Arm or leg

Sensory: Normal

CSF: Pleocytosis, Protein: \pm Increased

MRI: May show signal (T2) in spinal cord

Prognosis: Permanent paralysis

This Luxol-fast-blue stain of spinal cord in a patient with ALS demonstrates lateral column degeneration with gliosis--the "sclerosis" of ALS.

